

Flat Emission Silicon Nitride Grating Couplers for Lidar Optical Antennas

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Abstract: Light detection and ranging (Lidar) is a key enabling technology for autonomous vehicles and drones. Its emerging implementations are based on photonic integrated circuits (PICs) and optical phased arrays (OPAs). In this work we introduce a novel approach to the design of OPA Lidar antennas based on Si₃N₄ grating couplers. The well-established TriPleX platform and the asymmetric double stripe waveguide geometry with full etching are employed, ensuring low complexity and simple fabrication, combined with the low-loss advantages of the platform. The design study aims to optimize the performance of the grating coupler based radiators as well as the OPA, thus enhancing the overall capabilities of Si₃N₄ based Lidar. Uniform and non-uniform grating structures are considered, achieving θ and φ angles divergence of 0.9° and 32°, and 0.54° and 25.41° respectively. Also, wavelength sensitivity of 7°/100 nm is achieved. Last, the fundamental OPA parameters are investigated, and 35 dBi of peak directivity is achieved for an 8-element OPA.

Keywords: Grating Coupler, Lidar, Optical Phased Array, Optical Radiator, Silicon Nitride

1. Introduction

Autonomous vehicles, terrestrial and airborne, have gained popularity in recent years, with the automation use cases spreading across multiple sectors and industries. Their existing and foreseen applications range from the automotive and mobility industry with self-driving cars and automated taxis, to aerospace (automated urban air mobility (UAM) scenarios) and drones [1], smart cities, logistics, manufacturing, industrial applications and healthcare [2]. Since autonomous vehicles operate in dynamic environments, they rely on the use of advanced sensorial technologies for mapping [3], like the radio detection and ranging (Radar) and light detection and ranging (Lidar). Extensive research has taken place in recent years to advance the performance and co-integrate Radar and Lidar sensors for autonomous vehicles [4-5].

Lidar is a three-dimensional (3D) imaging, mapping and remote sensing technique that relies on optical beam shaping and steering [6] and has emerged as a promising solution for autonomous vehicles and drones. High performance Lidar systems compatible with such applications need to enable long-range power transmission with low cost, low power consumption, compact and robust implementations [7]. The high performance

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relies on increased field of view (FOV), high angular resolution, small beam divergence and increased scanning speed [8]. Traditionally, Lidar systems have been based on mechanical implementations with free-space optics and rotating parts [9] that however are not compatible with the compact size, low cost and reliability requirements, and have limited scanning speed [10]. Micro-electro-mechanical system (MEMS) Lidar is a more compact alternative, showcasing, though, reduced FOV and vulnerability to mechanical shocks. Solid-state Lidar has emerged in recent years as another technique that provides a scalable and reliable solution that does not include any moving mechanical parts [11]. It includes optical phased arrays (OPAs) where the beam is steered by waveguides instead of moving parts [12], or Flash Lidar that works like a camera and captures the image by illuminating the whole FOV [11]. However, a tradeoff exists also for these methods, as they showcase limited steering angle and detection range respectively.

In recent years, photonic integrated circuit (PIC) based Lidar has been gaining momentum [13]. The typical choice for PIC based Lidar is the Silicon on insulator (SOI) platform [10, 14-15] where the beam shaping and steering are performed by the silicon chip with the help of integrated phase shifters and OPAs based on grating elements. A schematic of an optical antenna in OPA configuration based on grating couplers is shown in Figure 1. This platform offers many advantages. Being compatible with standard mature complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) fabrication processes it enables the development of cost efficient, low power, reliable and robust Lidar systems, based on highly integrated OPAs [16]. Compact grating antennas based on one-dimensional (1D) OPAs can achieve two-dimensional (2D) beam steering by wavelength tuning along the longitudinal direction, and by phase control along the lateral dimension [16-17]. The inherent ultra-high index contrast of the SOI platform allows for beam steering as high as 15° with 100 nm wavelength tuning [18]. However, Silicon (Si) PICs require precise control of their components dimensions for optimal performance and are therefore susceptible to fabrication process errors. Moreover, the SOI platform cannot support high input power levels due to the appearance of non linear effects in Si, prohibiting its use in high power systems [19]. This limits the application of SOI PIC based Lidar.

Capitalizing on the advances of SOI-based Lidar, the Silicon Nitride (Si_3N_4) platform can enhance and further improve the capabilities and performance of PIC based Lidar. The Si_3N_4 platform showcases very low propagation losses and is compatible with high input optical power applications due to its low nonlinearities [20]. In combination with its low index contrast, this platform is robust to fabrication-induced phase variations. Moreover, it is transparent at wavelengths below 1150 nm [21] and showcases reduced emission strength for increased emitter length and small divergence [22], making it an interesting alternative to SOI for the development Lidar optical antennas [23]. The Lionix TripleX waveguide technology is one of the most well-established Si_3N_4 platforms. Among the different waveguide geometries it offers [24], the asymmetric double stripe (ADS) combines the ultra-low loss advantages of the platform with the lowest minimum bend radii, requiring simpler fabrication processes and offering higher yield compared to the other geometries [25]. Moreover, it is compatible with standard multi project wafer (MPW) fabrication processes employing single etch depth, and is highly suitable for applications that require coupling to external components such as active materials. This is especially important for Lidar applications, where the co-integration of the Si_3N_4 components with other photonic or electronic chips and components (e.g. indium phosphide for the realization of optical sources) can enable the development of complete Lidar and Radar systems.

However, the Si_3N_4 has its own limitations. Adequate beam steering by wavelength tuning remains a challenge due to the limited material dispersion. Recent developments have shown that steering angles of up to 7° for 100 nm tuning range can be achieved [22].

Moreover, the Si₃N₄ based Lidar is not a mature technology. Although various studies investigate Si₃N₄ optical antennas for Lidar [26-27] advances are still required to achieve the desired performance combining low divergence, uniform emission profiles and long length gratings with standard fabrication techniques. This is especially relevant for Si₃N₄ Lidar antennas employing the ADS waveguide geometry that have not yet been explored in literature. However, many applications can benefit from such implementations, thanks to their aforementioned advantages, making the research of ADS based Si₃N₄ optical radiators highly desirable and impactful.

This paper introduces a new approach to the design of grating couplers (GC) for Lidar optical antennas in the TriPleX Si₃N₄ platform, employing the ADS geometry. The effort focuses on achieving high performance of OPA based radiators for Lidar systems that can be employed in autonomous vehicles and drones, meeting the demanding requirements of such applications. More specifically, this design study targets high FOV of the OPAs, increased resolution and low receiver losses. The resolution depends on the beam divergence, and it can be improved by minimizing the beam divergence across the longitudinal and lateral directions (theta (θ) and phi (φ) angles divergence respectively). The beam divergence is determined by the optical aperture of the antenna, and also correlates to the radiation uniformity throughout the antenna length. In general, θ angle divergence depends on the design of the individual grating elements, while the φ angle divergence depends on the aperture of the OPA. The receiver losses can be reduced by targeting a flat emission profile in the longitudinal direction and achieve gratings with long effective areas (long gratings) that can collect light with increased efficiency. At the same time, this work targets Si₃N₄ optical radiators that are compatible with simple fabrication processes and single etch depth, fabricable through MPWs, without requiring access to more advanced techniques. Although this will signify limitations in the achieved performance, it ensures that the designs are low cost and easily fabricable, a requirement necessary in many applications. This is ensured with the use of the ADS geometry with single full etch depth. The design process outlined in this paper consists of two parts. The first concerns the design and optimization of the single grating element, to achieve uniform emission across long length and reduce the angles divergence. The second step targets the optimization of the OPA structure.

2. Layerstack and Antenna Design Considerations

The platform for the development of the optical radiators is the Lionix Si₃N₄ TriPleX platform [24-25] and the ADS waveguide geometry. The multiple layers of Si₃N₄ and Silicon Dioxide (SiO₂) allow to make low index contrast waveguides which is beneficial for reduced sensitivity of the waveguided modes effective refractive index (n_{eff}) to the waveguide geometry variation [23]. This results in reduced emission strength and allows to achieve long gratings. A cross-section of the ADS layerstack is shown in Figure 2(b). The bottom and top Si₃N₄ layer thickness is 75 nm and 175 nm respectively, while the distance between the two layers is 100 nm. The refractive index of the materials is $n_{SiO_2} = 1.44537$ and $n_{Si_3N_4} = 1.98350$ at 1550 nm. For realizing the grating teeth, full etching is employed (removal of both layers of the Si₃N₄ ADS layerstack), a limitation imposed by the available fabrication process. Adhering to this limitation ensures that the proposed design is fabricable with standard fabrication processes and minimal fabrication risks. As a result, a fixed etching depth is considered. The nominal waveguide width (w) is 1.1 μ m, however this value has been varied in the designed components. The design study was carried out in the spectral range 1500 nm – 1600 nm, centered around 1550 nm.

Figure 1: Schematic of an optical antenna in OPA configuration based on grating couplers. The θ and φ angles and the distance d between adjacent GC elements are noted.

Figure 2: (a) The OPA schematic to indicate the cross-sectional planes. (b) Schematic of the yz-plane cross-section of the standard TriPleX ADS waveguide. The different regions (Si₃N₄ waveguide, SiO₂ top oxide layer (TOX) and bottom oxide layer (BOX) and air top cladding) are marked with different colors. (c) Schematic of the sideview (xz-plane cross-section) of a periodic grating structure. The grating pitch is denoted with Λ and the filling factor with FF . The effective index of the etched part is n_0 and of the unetched part is n_1 .

The proposed GCs serve as the single radiator elements (building blocks) of the optical antenna and act as the light emitters and receivers of the Lidar. They are arranged linearly in series, one next to the other with distance d , in a linear 1D OPA configuration, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1 illustrates the θ and φ angles, along the longitudinal and lateral direction of the OPA respectively. The 1D OPA can realize beam steering in both directions, by tuning the wavelength in the longitudinal direction (θ) and by introducing a phase shift across the grating antenna along the lateral direction (φ). The advantage of this configuration is that 2D beam steering is ensured with an 1D structure, resulting in a significant reduced footprint (orders of magnitude less) on the chip compared to an equivalent 2D structure, considering that for a given aperture size 2D OPA requires N^2 elements instead of N elements for the 1D OPA. Moreover, in 2D OPAs, the on-chip real estate is increased due to the overhead of the phase shifters required for beam steering in both directions.

3. Design of Single Radiator Element

The building block of the proposed OPA Lidar optical antenna is the GC. The first part of this study focuses on the design and optimization of the GC based emitter using

the Lumerical finite difference eigenmode (FDE) and finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) solvers. Various configurations have been explored, including uniform and non-uniform geometries, to optimize the performance of the single radiator element.

3.1. Principle of Operation

Among the grating parameters, the most relevant for this design study that will be used in the design process are the effective refractive index of the grating period ($n_{eff-grating}$), the emission angle (θ) and the coupling constant (k).

In a grating structure, the effective index of a grating period that consists of an unetched part with effective refractive index of the supported mode n_1 and an etched part with effective refractive index of the supported mode n_0 , with filling factor FF , as shown in Figure 2(c), is given by (1)

$$n_{eff-grating} = FF * n_1 + (1 - FF) * n_0. \quad (1)$$

For our structure, since the etched part consists only of SiO₂ due to full etching, we assume the effective refractive index in the etched part to be equal to the refractive index of SiO₂ ($n_0 = n_{SiO_2}$).

The emission angle θ of a grating is related to the pitch Λ , the operating wavelength λ and the $n_{eff-grating}$, according to the Bragg condition expressed in (2) [28]

$$\sin(\theta) = \frac{n_{eff-grating} * \frac{\lambda}{\Lambda}}{n_{SiO_2}}. \quad (2)$$

The coupling constant k expresses the effective refractive index contrast between the high and low index sections of a grating period [27] and is given by (3).

$$k = \frac{n_1 - n_0}{n_{eff-grating} * \Lambda}. \quad (3)$$

k relates to how fast (over how many periods) the power will be scattered outside of the GC. For low loss waveguide platforms, having low k can help realize GCs with long effective lengths. One way to achieve low k is by varying the waveguide width along the GC length [29]. In applications that target uniform emission profiles, apodization of k along the length is desirable for engineering the emission profile.

3.2. Uniform Design

The simplest GC configuration in terms of design and fabrication complexity is a uniform GC where the geometrical parameters (filling factor (FF), width, pitch (Λ)), chosen for optimal performance, remain constant throughout the GC length. The effective index of the grating ($n_{eff-grating}$), given by (1), is also constant across a uniform design. Uniform GC configurations were investigated and simulated in this study. A topview of the uniform grating is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Sideview of the uniform GC, showing the constant pitch, FF and width across the direction of propagation.

Figure 4: Simulated θ and φ angles divergence (a) varying the grating width for fixed length of 92.6 μm and (b) varying the grating length for fixed width of 2 μm .

For the design proposed in this paper, FF was chosen equal to 0.5. The next parameter that was investigated is the width. The nominal width in this platform is 1.1 μm , and its minimum value for proper confinement of the mode in the waveguide is 700 nm. Hence, width values greater than 1 μm were investigated. The waveguide width affects the light confinement within the waveguide in the lateral dimension. At the same time, large width values increase the required distance (d) between adjacent GCs (shown in Figure 1) in the OPA to avoid evanescent field coupling and cross-talk between the OPA channels. Last, as the width increases, we enter the multi-mode regime, which should be avoided. Therefore, a study of the width impact on the OPA performance (angles divergence) is necessary to optimize its value. To this end, 3D-FDTD simulations were performed varying the waveguide width between 1 μm and 4 μm with step of 0.5 μm , while keeping the other parameters constant (length = 92.6 μm , $FF = 0.5$). The simulated θ and φ angles 3dB divergence is shown in Figure 4(a). These results indicate that as the width increases, the φ divergence will decrease (10.4% of decrease for width variation between 1 and 4 μm), while θ divergence is monotonically affected (9% of increase for width variation between 1 and 4 μm). Since the θ divergence is close to 1°, this translates to 0.1° of change, that is considered small in terms of absolute value for the application. Taking into account the aforementioned limitations and to ensure that the spacing requirements in the OPA structure will remain reasonable, width up to 2 μm should be chosen.

As a second step, the effect of the GC length variation is studied, to optimize its value. 3D-FDTD were performed, this time varying the GC length between 25 μm and 200 μm , while keeping the width constant to 2 μm and the FF to 0.5. The resulting simulated θ and φ angles 3dB divergence is shown in Figure 4(b). We observe that both the θ and φ divergence is reduced as the length increases. For length of 92.6 μm , the θ divergence is 0.94°, while the φ divergence is 33.92°. For lengths longer than 160 μm the divergence values start to converge. For length of 208 μm values for the θ and φ divergence as low as 0.63° and 28° can be achieved. This signifies a θ and φ divergence reduction of 81% and 55.5% respectively, for the investigated length increase from 25 μm to 200 μm .

Figure 5: Left: topview of the emission profile of the uniform grating for width of 2 μm and length of 100 μm . The E_z component field distribution is shown with the color scale. Right: 1D plot of the emission profile along the dashed line of the left figure.

Figure 6: Calculated emission angle θ of the farfield profile, varying the wavelength in the range 1.5 - 1.6 μm , for uniform teeth profile and pitch 926 nm. The electric field intensity is shown with the colour scale.

Last, the pitch is freely chosen according to (2), to achieve the desired emission angle. For emission angle of around -10° , which is a typical value for radiators, the pitch is set to 926 nm. These values result in optimal performance of the uniform grating, while minimizing the θ and φ angle divergence. A 3D-FDTD simulation was repeated with the selected geometrical parameters. The topview and sideview of the simulated emission profile of the grating are shown in Figure 5. The extracted θ and φ angles divergence is 0.9° and 32° respectively. It is worth noting that the φ divergence is large because these simulations do not take into account the complete OPA structure, but only the single radiator element.

Figure 6 illustrates the θ angle wavelength sensitivity as extracted from the farfield data. With the uniform design, 7° of θ angle wavelength steering is achieved, with 100 nm of wavelength shift, from 1500 nm to 1600 nm. However, it is evident from Figure 5 that this component has an exponential emission profile and cannot meet the design target of uniform emission and long effective length. This is expected because the uniform design has a constant k , and given that every period receives less input light than the previous, due to the light that is emitted upwards, the resulting emission profile will showcase an exponential decay. Therefore, to achieve more uniform emission profiles, non-uniform grating profiles have been investigated, as described in the next paragraph.

3.3. Non-uniform Design

Due to the performance limitations of the uniform design, non-uniform configurations were also investigated to achieve more uniform emission profiles. The non-uniformity concerns the geometrical parameters of the design and suggests that along the grating length some of the design parameters are being varied. Taking into account the fabrication process limitations, and to ensure compatibility with Lionix TriPLeX platform fabrication processes that enable only full etching, the parameters that can be varied are the waveguide width, the filling factor and the pitch.

The geometry variation of the non uniform grating is designed to ensure a constant emission angle θ across the grating length, for low θ angle divergence and increased resolution in the longitudinal axis. According to (1) and (2), to ensure a constant emission angle the induced geometry variation needs to be designed carefully. In this study we vary the width and FF , keeping the pitch value constant, and considering only fully etched waveguides. A topview and a sideview of the non-uniform design are shown in Figure 7 left and right respectively. Moreover, the geometry variation targets uniform emission distributions. To achieve this, the k of every period should gradually increase across the grating length. Increasing k is achieved by decreasing the FF (to approach FF of 0.5 that

results in stronger emission) and increasing the width across the grating length, which leads to increasing emission rate [27].

Figure 7: (Left) topview and (Right) sideview of the investigated non-uniform grating design with varying width and FF .

Figure 8: Calculated effective refractive index of the TE_0 mode varying the waveguide width.

The design process started with FDE simulations using Lumerical MODE solver. First, the effective index of the fundamental TE mode of a waveguide cross-section (n_1) varying its width, is calculated, given the ADS TriPleX layerstack. The results are shown in Figure 8. In the ADS TriPleX platform, to create the grating teeth the Si_3N_4 is fully etched, removing both layers of the Si_3N_4 layerstack that are illustrated in Figure 2(b). Therefore, the etched part of the grating geometry consists of SiO_2 . Since there is no waveguiding material in the etched part and the FDE solver cannot calculate any supported modes, we assume the value of the effective refractive index of the etched part (n_0) to be equal to the value of the refractive index of SiO_2 (n_{SiO_2}). Using (1) and the calculated n_1 values, it is then possible to compute the $n_{eff-grating}$, for the different width and FF combinations. This is shown in Figure 9.

From the results shown in Figure 9 it is evident that for specific pairs of waveguide width and FF , the $n_{eff-grating}$ remains constant. These contour lines, shown with black lines in Figure 9, are the desired regions from which the width- FF pairs can be extracted. The design methodology includes partitioning the available width range in N values to produce the width- FF pairs, as it will be described shortly. Thus, it is ensured that the emission angle θ is also constant. Moreover, the emission profile of the grating is no longer exponential, but becomes more uniform. This is achieved because across the grating length the FF decreases approaching 0.5, while the width increases, leading to an increasing k . For a given contour line, the corresponding coupling constant k has been calculated according to (3). Figure 10 illustrates k for three of the contour lines of Figure 9. It can be observed that for all contour lines, k is similar, and it gradually increases as the width increases, according to the design target.

Figure 9: $n_{\text{eff-grating}}$ of the fundamental supported mode calculated via FDE simulations, varying the waveguide width and FF . The black lines are the contour lines of the plots along which the $n_{\text{eff-grating}}$ has a constant value. The selected contour line is marked with the pink stars.

Figure 10: The calculated coupling constant k for the different width values across the grating, for three of the contour lines.

It is noted that there are multiple contour lines one can work with. A choice between the available options must therefore be made targeting optimal performance. In terms of keeping the emission angle constant, all contour lines are equivalent. However, there are two more criteria that can help make the best choice.

The first one concerns the compatibility of the design with the fabrication process capabilities. The FF should remain below 0.9 for compatibility with the acceptable minimum feature size of approximately 100 nm (for pitch around 1 μm , FF should be between 0.1 and 0.9). Moreover, the FF step should be as large as possible, leading to large steps in the grating teeth length and compatibility with the minimum step size. This is satisfied when choosing a contour line with large slope in the whole width range. The same is true in the lateral direction where large width steps are desirable for compatibility with minimum step size. For a given GC length (fixed amount of GC periods and partitioning steps N), increasing the utilized width range will increase the width step. Note that we choose to work with width larger than 1 μm for proper confinement of the fundamental mode within the waveguide. Moreover, widths larger than 2 μm are not desirable since they impose limitations in the spacing between the array elements and full OPA size, and also signify operation in the multimode regime.

A second criterion for choosing the contour line is the k value. Although between the different contour lines the k values are similar, we see from Figure 10 that k shows a larger variation in the 1-1.5 μm width range, compared to the 1.5-2 width range. Therefore, there is a trade-off between having a larger k variation and an acceptable width size. All things considered, the contour line that best fits all criteria is marked with pink stars in Figure 9 and has $n_{\text{eff-grating}}=1.495$.

After choosing the contour line, a polynomial fit is performed to extract the function that can then be used to calculate the width- FF pairs that will constitute the geometrical parameters of the design. To do this the desired number of grating periods N is chosen, then N width values are sampled in the available width range and according to the polynomial function the corresponding FF values are computed. During this design study, we have investigated multiple approaches with the 1-1.5 μm and 1-2 μm width ranges and have selected multiple contour line plots, both in the width range 1-1.5 μm and in the width range 1-2 μm , for comparison. The simulation results indicate that they all show-case similar performance and different designs have been considered for fabrication, to allow to experimentally validate their performance. In the rest of the paper, we show the results of a design with $n_{\text{eff-grating}}=1.495$ and width range 1-2 μm .

Having defined the width- FF pairs, the rest of geometrical parameters, namely the pitch and the length (or equivalently the number of grating periods N) need also to be set. As with the uniform design, the pitch can be freely chosen according to the desired emission angle. It must be noted that at higher emission angles the θ wavelength sensitivity is increased. This is due to Snell's law at the air/SiO₂ cladding interface. This was verified with simulations that show a steering angle wavelength sensitivity of around 6°/100 nm for $\theta \sim 0^\circ$ and 11°/100 nm for $\theta \sim 40^\circ$. However, such large emission angles render the emitters difficult to operate on a system level, imposing strict requirements in terms of packaging. This results in a trade-off between steering angle wavelength sensitivity and the complexity of packaging and system operation, and depending on the application the appropriate choice should be made. In this case, for emission angle of -10° , 926 nm pitch is calculated, according to (2).

Concerning the number of grating periods N , this can also be freely chosen. Given the pitch, N will define the complete length of the grating (L) as $L = \text{pitch} \cdot N$. However, a trade-off also exists between the two parameters. On one hand, gratings with long length are needed for increased efficiency, long effective areas and small θ angle divergence. On the other hand, increasing the length (and therefore N) results in reducing the step size both in the width and length dimensions. This happens because the width and FF pairs are limited both by the contour lines and from the limited ranges [1 μm - 2 μm] and [0.1 - 0.9] respectively as explained before. As a result, to have more periods these ranges need to be partitioned into more parts, resulting in smaller step sizes. This threatens the GC fabricability with standard fabrication processes and might lead to mis fabrications and degraded performance. To verify the effect of the length variation in the performance of the grating, multiple 3D-FDTD simulations were performed, keeping the rest of the parameters constant. The results are shown in Figure 11. We observe that as the length increases, the θ and φ divergences decrease. For $L=93.52 \mu\text{m}$ ($N=100$), θ 3dB divergence is 0.9° , and φ is 32.25° . For $L=186.13 \mu\text{m}$ ($N=200$), θ 3dB divergence is 0.54° , and φ is 25.41° . For larger widths, θ and φ divergences converge. This translates to a θ and φ divergence reduction of 87% and 57.4% respectively, for the investigated length increase from 25 μm to 235 μm . The rest of the simulation results are produced for $N=200$.

Figure 11: Simulated θ and φ angles divergence varying the grating length, for width- FF pairs calculated from the same contour line.

Figure 12: Left: topview of the emission profile of the non-uniform grating for the selected geometrical parameters. The E_z component field distribution is shown with the color scale. Right: 1D plot of the emission profile along the dashed line of the left figure.

Having defined all the geometrical parameters of the GC, a 3D-FDTD simulation of the selected configuration was performed with Lumerical FDTD solver. Figure 12 illustrates the emission profile of the proposed non-uniform grating. It is observed that the emission profile is more uniform compared to the uniform design. Figure 13 shows the θ angle wavelength sensitivity for pitch of 926 nm, revealing a steering angle of $7^\circ/100$ nm.

Figure 13: Calculated emission angle θ of the farfield profile, varying the wavelength in the range 1.5 - 1.6 μm , for the non-uniform teeth profile and pitch 926 nm. The electric field intensity is shown with the colour scale.

4. Design of the OPA Structure

After the design of the single radiator element is performed, we simulate the OPA structure and optimize its parameters, the number of elements in the antenna (NA) and their distance (d), defined as the center-to-center distance between two adjacent elements. This simulation is performed with the Sensor Array Analyzer toolbox by Matlab, a toolbox that allows to create and simulate OPA structures and antennas, extracting the radiation patterns and the θ and φ angles divergence.

More specifically, we have varied NA between 2 and 8, and d between 1 and 2λ , where λ is the center wavelength and equals 1.55 μm . We investigate the variation profile of the values of directivity, θ and φ angles divergence, while scaling the NA value.

We choose to work with up NA to 8, however the design process is applicable to much higher NA values (e.g. 1024), only restricted by chip real estate and packaging considerations. The resulting radiation plots are shown in Figure 14, given the radiation pattern of the selected non-uniform design of Figure 12. We can extract the θ angle divergence by examining the elevation cut of the directivity plots, for azimuthal angle equal to 0° . Such elevation cuts are shown in Figure 15, for two different OPA configurations. For the different antenna configurations of Figure 14, the θ 3 dB divergence is approximately

0.58°. This is illustrated in Figure 15 where the 3 dB region around the peak directivity value is marked with the pink vertical arrows, and the corresponding θ divergence is marked with the horizontal red lines and equals 0.58°. This is in agreement with the results from the 3D-FDTD simulations and it confirms that θ is not affected by NA , d , but rather depends on the design of the individual grating elements.

Figure 14: 3D directivity plots (in dBi) produced with Sensor Array Analyzer app, varying the number (NA) of grating elements and the distance (d) between them.

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Figure 15: Elevation cut for azimuth angle = 0°, for two of the directivity plots of Figure 14.

On the other hand, the divergence of the φ angle is affected by the OPA topology, both by the number of elements NA and by their distance d . Increasing the NA reduces the φ divergence of the main lobe. Also, increasing the distance between adjacent elements reduces the main lobe φ divergence. It can also be seen in Figure 14 that increasing the number of elements (for a fixed distance) will result in the appearance of more side lobes, with lower peak directivities, while the width of the main lobe is reduced. A similar effect is observed when the number of elements is kept constant, and their distance is increased. In this case more side lobes appear, and their peak directivity is also increased. Last, from the directivity plots the peak directivity value can be extracted. This is 34.8 dBi for $NA=4$ and $d=1.5\lambda$, and 35 dBi for $NA=8$ and $d=1.5\lambda$.

It is evident that a trade-off exists between the number of side lobes, their peak directivities and the width of the main lobe, that corresponds to the φ divergence. Depending on the application, and whether emphasis needs to be given to either minimize the φ divergence or the number and size of side lobes, an appropriate design choice can be made for NA and d .

Is it worth noting that there is another limiting factor of the distance d . That is the cross-talk between adjacent grating elements which is affected both by the waveguide widths as well as their distance. If d is too small and the grating length adequate for the power to couple from one grating to the other, there will be interference that will degrade the performance. To estimate this effect FDE simulations were performed in which two waveguides were placed one next to the other and the L_{10} , which is the length required for 10% of the power to couple from waveguide 1 to waveguide 2, was calculated. This simulation was done for different values of d and across the entire range of the investigated grating widths. The results are shown in Figure 16. To interpret the results, two things have to be considered that act simultaneously and affect the value of L_{10} . On one hand, for smaller width, the same d (x-axis in Figure 16) means bigger distance between the waveguides. At the same time, bigger width means better confinement of the mode in the waveguide, and therefore smaller interaction between the adjacent waveguides. These two factors have opposite effects on the value of L_{10} .

Figure 16: Calculated L_{10} varying the distance d between two adjacent waveguides with width 1 μm , 1.5 μm and 2 μm .

Overall, Table 1 summarizes the results extracted from Figure 16. The results indicate that for distance d bigger than 2λ ($3.1\ \mu\text{m}$), the L_{10} is larger than $200\ \mu\text{m}$, therefore for shorter lengths no crosstalk is expected. For spacing of 2.5λ ($\sim 3.8\ \mu\text{m}$) L_{10} is very large so no crosstalk will appear in this case. For the proposed GC that have lengths shorter than $200\ \mu\text{m}$, 2 and 2.5λ distances can be chosen. However, if the distance is only 1.5λ then L_{10} is very low and below $50\ \mu\text{m}$. For OPAs with this d some crosstalk between adjacent waveguides is expected. Therefore, although having small spacing d between the gratings, which minimizes the unwanted sidelobes, might be preferred in some applications, 1 or 1.5λ spacing might not be feasible since it will lead to inevitable crosstalk between the adjacent waveguides, degrading the signal. This aspect must be taken into account when choosing the antenna parameters, depending always on the needs of every application.

Table 1. Calculated L_{10} for the different width and distance combinations as extracted from Figure 16.

width \ d	$1.5\ \lambda$	$2\ \lambda$	$2.5\ \lambda$
$1\ \mu\text{m}$	$45\ \mu\text{m}$	$250\ \mu\text{m}$	$1400\ \mu\text{m}$
$1.5\ \mu\text{m}$	$40\ \mu\text{m}$	$300\ \mu\text{m}$	$2280\ \mu\text{m}$
$2\ \mu\text{m}$	$20\ \mu\text{m}$	$185\ \mu\text{m}$	$1600\ \mu\text{m}$

5. Conclusions

In this study, we propose a methodology that can be exploited for the design of flat emission PIC based optical antennas. We apply this methodology to design and optimize a Si_3N_4 optical antenna based on the ADS geometry, employing only full etching. The study focuses first on optimizing the single radiator element, targeting a constant emission angle, low θ and φ angles divergence and uniform emission profile. Both uniform and non-uniform geometries were investigated, showcasing θ and φ angles divergence of 0.9° and 32° , and 0.54° and 25.41° respectively. Also, wavelength sensitivity of $7^\circ/100\ \text{nm}$ was achieved. Last, the OPA structure was optimized, and the effect of the NA and d parameters was investigated. For 8 elements in the OPA, we achieve $35\ \text{dBi}$ of peak directivity.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

Lidar	Light detection and ranging
PIC	Photonic integrated circuit
OPA	Optical phased array
UAM	Automated urban air mobility
Radar	Radio detection and ranging
3D	Three-dimensional
FOV	Field of view
MEMS	Micro-electromechanical system
SOI	Silicon-on-insulator
CMOS	Complementary metal-oxide semiconductor
1D	One-dimensional
2D	Two-dimensional
Si_3N_4	Silicon Nitride
ADS	Asymmetric double stripe
MPW	Multi-project wafer
GC	Grating coupler

SiO ₂	Silicon dioxide
n _{eff}	Effective refractive index
FDE	Finite difference eigenmode
FDTD	Finite-difference time-domain
FF	Filling factor

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